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MOURNING IN THE TIME OF COVID-19: STRATEGIES FOR FIGHTING PAIN AND PSYCHIC SUFFERING OF THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 originated in China, with a high transmission capacity made a rapid emergence of the pandemic. With everyone very concerned about knowing the virus and all its procedures, mental health was the least notoriety, causing many to have deficiencies in this area. The present study aims to describe the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief, discuss the psychosocial impacts of mourning Covid-19, therefore, the focus is always on mental health in relation to the grief experienced. This is an integrative literature review study. The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of coping strategies for pain and psychic suffering of the population in the face of grief, since few manage to reach the service having to resort to alternative methods, also having a great perception that the number of professionals eligible for this action are extremely low. Through this study, we hope to help more health professionals pay attention to the mistakes previously made during the pandemic and encourage changes in the quality of care provided to the grieving population, not only during a pandemic, but at all times of mourning.